

Job and personal resources: boosting work engagement and job satisfaction in hospitals

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ABSTRACT

The low level of job satisfaction (JS) among hospital staff is associated with the low level of work engagement (WE). To examine WE, the Job demand-resources theory is often applied. This study aims to see the effect of job resources (JR) and personal resources (PR) on WE and their impact on JS. This is a quantitative study that takes a cross-sectional method. The sample consisted of 244 employees of the Haji Hospital Makassar in South Sulawesi Province who were selected by random quota sampling and then analyzed using the Path Analysis test on SPSS AMOS 26. The results showed that JR (p-value 0.002<0.005, E=0.131) and PR (p-value 0.001<0.005, E=0.170) had a significant effect on WE. JR has a direct influence on JS (p-value 0.022<0.005, E=0.375). Although the indirect effect of JR on JS work engagement (WE) through is not significant (p-value 0.065<0.005), meanwhile, PR has a significant direct (p-value 0.001<0.005, E=0.248) and indirect (p-value 0.035<0.005, E=0.047) effect on JS. This study concludes that the direct influence path of PR is the best path for enhancing employee JS in hospitals.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction (JS) is a worldwide issue because of its potential impact on patient care quality and safety. Health service providers are mostly responsible for the quality of performance in the healthcare industry, including hospitals. Job satisfaction is an important topic of research since it predicts improved job performance, work ethics, and worker enthusiasm, as well as lower absenteeism, tiredness, and turnover [1]. This is due to the fact that when internal consumers (hospital staff) are satisfied, they are more inclined to provide high-quality service to their external customers [2]. Based on previous research, the condition of JS in hospitals is still a problem [3], [4].

The provincial government-owned hospital is one of the public sector organizations that has a strategic role in the complete implementation of individual health. Based on the results of previous research conducted at the Haji Hospital Makassar in South Sulawesi Province in 2022, it showed that employee job satisfaction had not reached the standard, namely only 70.80% (standard: 76.61%-88.30%). Low job satisfaction can have an impact on employee performance [5], the desire to leave the job [3], and higher

levels of burnout [6]. Based on this description, the researcher is then interested in examining the things that can increase job satisfaction at the Haji Hospital Makassar in South Sulawesi Province.

Work engagement is also known to predict job satisfaction [7]. Several studies have stated that work engagement affects job satisfaction in hospitals [8]–[10]. Employees who are engaged are seen as more enthusiastic and consider their jobs a challenge. Workers who are dedicated and motivated play a significant role in providing high-quality care in any health-care system [11]. Since work engagement is essential to enhancing one's performance at work, it is currently a crucial issue in achieving organizational effectiveness [12].

Work engagement is discussed in several theories. To examine work engagement, however, the job demands-resources theory (JD-R theory) is frequently applied. According to JD-R theory, a number of factors, including job demands and job resources, affect how motivated employees are at work [13]. The equilibrium between job demand and job resources can result in work engagement, and the work engagement produced by these circumstances may be the basis of the job satisfaction that develops. Another assumption of the JD-R model is that personal resources, like job resources, can be used to predict work engagement. Employees' positive self-beliefs and sense of control over their work environment are referred to as personal resources [14].

Based on the previous explanation, the purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of job resources (JR) and personal resources (PR) on employee work engagement (WE), as well as their impact on JS. The findings of this study will explain the effects of JR and PR on WE and JS, which is a necessary first step in identifying and modifying the most effective interventions for hospital staff. As a result, the findings of this study are expected to serve as more than merely a scientific foundation for future research but also as a guide for hospitals on how to improve employee job satisfaction and engagement at work in order to have an impact on enhancing overall hospital performance.

2. METHOD

2.1. Study setting

This is a quantitative study using a cross-sectional design. This research was carried out in 2023 at the Haji Hospital Makassar in South Sulawesi Province. The population of this study was employees at the Haji Hospital Makassar in South Sulawesi Province, totaling 626 people, including doctors, dentists, nurses, midwives, pharmacists and pharmacist assistants, laboratory assistants, radiographers, nutritionists, physiotherapists, other health workers, management, and others. The sample size of 244 employees was obtained using the Slovin formula with a 5% margin of error. The sample count has reached the minimal number of samples required for quantitative research [15]. The sampling technique was random quota sampling, selected by criterion for inclusion and exclusion. The Ethics Commission of Hasanuddin University's Faculty of Public Health approved this study for ethical reasons (approval number: 3116/UN4.14.1/TP.01.02/2023).

2.2. Questionnaire and data analysis

In this study, likert scale questionnaires and interviews were utilized as instruments. JR are measured using several indicators, including autonomy, social support, and performance feedback. PR are measured using self-efficacy, organizational-based self-esteem, and optimism. WE is measured by the nine-item version of the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale. JS is measured by the job satisfaction questionnaire for the health workforce using 33 question items consisting of 8 indicators: leadership, training and development, teamwork, empowerment and participation, working conditions, reward and recognition, communication, and flexibility of working hours.

This instrument has been tested for construct validity and reliability using 30 respondents at Labuang Baji Hospital, Makassar. The reliability test results show that all question items in this research questionnaire are reliable, as seen from the Cronbach's alpha value of >0.80 . The validity test results show that all question items in the questionnaire are valid, as seen from the person correlation value $>r$ -table (0.361), which ranges from 0.362 to 0.873. Data analysis used the path analysis test using the SPSS AMOS 26 application. In this study, the data analysis findings were given in tabular form along with a narrative-style explanation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

Table 1 displays the demographics of respondents, including their age, gender, education, and work status. It shows that the respondents in this study were dominated by respondents aged 36–45 years, with as many as 97 people (39.8%). Based on gender, the respondents were dominated by women, with as many as 204 people (83.6), while the remaining 40 were male (16.4%). The education level of the respondents was

dominated by professions for as many as 92 people (37.7%), and most of the respondents had civil servant status for as many as 190 people (77.9%).

Table 1. Frequency distribution of respondent characteristics

Characteristics of respondents	Amount		Total
	n	%	
Age (years)			
20-35	90	36.9	244
36-45	97	39.8	
>45	57	23.4	
Gender			
Male	40	16.4	244
Female	204	83.6	
Education			
High school/Equivalent	3	1.2	244
D3/Equivalent	59	24.5	
D4/Bachelor/Equivalent	81	33.2	
Master degree	9	3.7	
Profession	92	37.7	
Employment status			
Civil servant	190	77.9	244
Special employee	11	4.5	
Contract employee	43	17.6	

The significance value of the JR variable for WE is $0.002 < 0.05$, according to the results of Table 2. These findings suggest that JR has a major impact on WE. The estimated value is 0.131, which means that the higher the JR, the more WE will increase by 13%. Then the significance value of the PR variable is $WE = 0.001 < 0.05$. These results indicate that PR has a significant effect on WE. The estimated value is 0.170, which means that the higher the PR owned by employees, the more WE will increase by 17%. Meanwhile, the significance value of the JR variable for JS is $0.022 < 0.05$. This means that JR has a significant effect on JS. The estimated value is 0.375, meaning that the higher the JR you have, the higher your JS will be by 37.5%. The significance value for the PR variable for JS is $0.001 < 0.05$. This shows that PR has a significant effect on JS. The estimated value is 0.250, which means that the higher the PR owned, the higher JS will be by 25.0%. In addition, the significance value of WE to JS is $0.001 < 0.05$. The estimated value is 0.280, which means that the higher the WE you have, the higher the JS of employees at the hospital will be (28%).

In addition, it is known that the significance value of the indirect effect provided by JR on JS is 0.065. This means that JR has no influence on JS through WE. Meanwhile, the significance value of the indirect effect exerted by PR on JS is 0.035. This means that PR has an influence on JS through WE. The estimated value of PR's indirect effect on JS through WE is 0.047, whereas the estimated value of PR's direct effect on JS is 0.250. This suggests that direct influence has a higher value than indirect impact. This finding indicates that PR has a direct impact on the JS condition of hospital staff.

Table 2. Path analysis test results for direct and indirect effects of job resources and personal resources on work engagement and employee job satisfaction

Variabel	Estimate	S.E.	p-value	Label
Job resources → Work engagement	.131	.042	.002	Significant
Personal resources → Work engagement	.170	.031	.001	Significant
Job resources → Job satisfaction	.375	.082	.022	Significant
Personal resources → Job satisfaction	.250	.062	.001	Significant
Work engagement → Job satisfaction	.280	.123	.001	Significant
Job resources → Work engagement → Job satisfaction	.036	.019	.065	Not significant
Personal resources → Work engagement → Job satisfaction	.047	.022	.035	Significant

3.2. Discussion

According to the findings of a study conducted on employees at the Haji Hospital Makassar in South Sulawesi Province, there is a favorable influence of JR on WE with an estimated value of 0.131. This demonstrates that JR have a strong beneficial effect on WE, with the higher the perceived JR by hospital staff, the greater the level of WE among employees. Other research have demonstrated a substantial association between JR and WE, as well as a direct and positive impact [16], [17]. Previous study indicates that employment resources have a positive impact on WE and can improve employee welfare [18]–[20].

Everyone's level of engagement at work varies. Depending on the number of resources that are offered in the workplace, engaged employees will focus more on their tasks [21]. According to the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model, JR act as a motivator, and each increase is associated with an increase in WE [22]. As a result, employees must always work in a supportive environment (defined by job autonomy, performance review, and social support). A previous study discovered that job feedback, together with task control, supervisor and colleague support, and a favorable social climate, is the most essential of the five JR [23]. Engagement at work will then increase as a result of these resources.

Furthermore, according to the findings of an investigation that used path analysis to look at the direct and indirect relationship between factors, JR variables had a direct impact on JS. As a result, WE does not play a role in mitigating the influence of JR on employee JS at Haji Hospital Makassar in South Sulawesi Province. In line with other studies that demonstrate how JR directly affect JS in hospitals. With around 1,100 clinical employees, employment resources seem to be more important in promoting improved JS in mental health services in Australia [24].

A study conducted on nurses showed a correlation between JS and work resources; more resources at work should result in higher nurse satisfaction. Because of the positive relationship between JD and JS, more JR may result in lower JD and better levels of nurse satisfaction. The findings also showed that supervisory assistance and occupational autonomy were provided to nurses, both of which improved their satisfaction [25]. This is supported by other studies that show that JR elements have an important positive correlation with JS [26].

According to the findings of a study conducted on employees at the Haji Hospital Makassar in South Sulawesi Province, PR had a favorable influence on work engagement, with an estimated value of 0.171. This reveals that PR have a major positive effect on WE, with higher perceived PR by hospital personnel resulting in better employee WE. This study supports that of Contreras *et al.* [27], who found that WE is significantly influenced by PR. Additionally, it is said that the best predictor of WE is the PR variable. According to this study, workers with high PR will be better able to handle situations that correspond to professional expectations and refrain from acting out.

Based on the above, WE may be encouraged by increasing workers' PR, thereby promoting processes of adaptability to hard and demanding work situations, which may operate as a preventative factor for burnout. Furthermore, the findings demonstrate that PR have a substantial impact on boosting JS among hospital staff. According to research, PR are important for JS [28]. To have an impact on enhancing employee WE and JS, this must be promoted in a targeted manner by focusing on the human resources of hospital workers.

According to the findings of the path analysis used to determine the direct and indirect impacts of variables, the PR variable has a direct and indirect effect on JS. Although the contribution of indirect effects is small when compared to the contribution of direct effects. The more positive a person feels about himself and the more self-compatibility he feels with a goal, the more PR he possesses. This is due to the fact that various personalities interpret JD-R differently, resulting in differences in WE [29].

Achieving a goal will be inherently motivating for those with this compatibility, which will ultimately lead to improved performance and happiness. Individuals, on the other hand, may attribute varying motivational values to the resources they employ to increase their levels of involvement [30]. In summary, when people are engaged at work, they have the personal assets of optimism, self-efficacy, and self-reliance that enable them to successfully influence their surroundings and advance their careers. Furthermore, hospital leadership styles are required to improve staff engagement by enhancing job resources and minimizing JD [31].

4. CONCLUSION

JR and PR can have a direct impact on employee JS in hospitals. Furthermore, despite the fact that the influence of these variables is minor, WE functions as a mediator between PR to promote JS among hospital personnel. JR and PR that influence employee JS. Therefore, hospital management is advised to pay more attention to JR for employees by motivating them, increasing social support in the workplace, and fostering and maintaining harmonious relations between superiors and employees. Additionally, it pays attention to the personal resources of employees by enhancing their abilities so that they can feel confident that they can successfully control and have an impact on their environment and that they can raise their level of engagement and JS. Future researchers should be able to use qualitative research techniques to delve deeper into the phenomena surrounding respondents' personal and professional resources, job happiness, work engagement, and employee performance.

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